

Efficient Rendering and Perception of Acoustical Environments in Augmented Reality Audio

Alex Baldwin

Dirac Research, Uppsala, Sweden
alex Baldwin music@gmail.com

Jonas Holfelt

GN Store Nord, Copenhagen, Denmark
jholfelt@gmail.com

Cumhur Erkut

Aalborg University Copenhagen
cer@create.aau.dk

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an efficient real-time estimation and rendering of an acoustical environment for augmented reality (AR). An AR application obtains information about a given environment based on the detected surfaces with the camera, as well as the positions virtual sound sources and listener. Then an artificial reverberator is calibrated based on these data. An evaluation is carried out both in an actual and in a virtual room (by using pre-rendered impulse responses and convolution). Results indicate a perceptual preference towards simpler artificial reverberators. Taken together, our implementation and perceptual evaluation results contribute to the challenge of real-time interaction in a real, dynamic environment so that the virtual objects are registered in that environment not only visually, but also in the auditory modality.

1. INTRODUCTION

Immersive experiences in virtual environments require realistic but efficient sound rendering algorithms [1]. The sound design pipeline for these experiences usually consist of three major elements: *source modeling*, *room acoustics modeling* and *listener modeling* [1]. In this paper, we focus on the room acoustics modeling. We implement some efficient delay-based algorithms first on Unity. We then deploy them to a mobile AR device prototype. We finally evaluate immersive sonic experiences.

Our work derives from two implementations. The first one is ScattAR [2]. The application allows the user to scan an environment from which a 3D mesh is generated. First-order reflection points were calculated using the image-source method [3]. The source and reflection points, and listener were connected according to Scattering Delay Network (SDN) technique [4], and reverberation was calculated. Both the listener and sound source can be moved around in space, while reflections were updated in real time. Fig. 1 depicts ScattAR, where a sound source (drone) moves in an actual (left) or virtual (right) room, and the direct path (green) as well as first-order reflections (red paths) are calculated, visualized, and auralized.

Recent work has shown interest in modeling sparsely reflecting scenes and proposed a solution utilizing the Digital

Waveguide Web (WGW) [5]. The model is highly flexible, but computational costs increase exponentially with added scattering junctions. WGWs were added by Jonas Holfelt to the ScattAR framework [6]. Computational benchmarks of WGWs in our framework indicates that even the simplest cases using just five reflection points are computationally too demanding for real-time implementation.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows. First, ScattAR is a valuable application in teaching and demonstrating room acoustics, and we hope to maintain the development by porting it to other AR-frameworks. This requires a compact description of previous implementations for reference. Second, besides comparing the simulated environments to the original ones, we clearly need different strategies in conducting interactive listening tests. In ScattAR, an interactive perceptual test on object presence indicated only a marginal difference between the ratings of SDN processed sound and unprocessed anechoic sound, favoring the SDN [7]. Recent tests indicate the difference is clearly perceivable in non-interactive conditions, and require intermediate steps as well as a more accurate model.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives a brief overview of important fundamental reverberation methods, followed by an overview of the SDN and WGW methods, which form the theory needed for the implementation. Section 3 describes the implementation of SDN and WGW. Section 4 presents an evaluation in a virtual environment. Finally, Section 5 discusses the results and concludes the paper.

2. BACKGROUND

This section presents two fundamental methods for artificial reverberation: *convolution-based algorithms* and *delay networks*. The former method is realistic but not flexible, whereas the latter represents the foundation for the implementation of both SDN and WGW. In this paper, they will be used in tandem, and the *image-source* method will also be utilized.

2.1 Convolution Reverb

Convolution reverb is performed by convolving a *room impulse response* (RIR) with a dry input signal. The RIR can be obtained either by a recording in a physical acoustic space, or by synthesis. The result is a very accurate reverberation model, though it is not flexible [8], plus it is computationally heavy. *Fast convolution techniques* have been proposed, where one solution is to multiply signals after

Figure 1. A virtual drone in a real-room on the ScattAR mobile augmented reality audio application. a) Left: Real-time path overlays of direct path (green) and first-order reflections (red). b) Right: Simulation on Unity.

FFT has been performed [8], thus simplifying the computation.

2.2 Image-Source Method

In the image-source method, physical boundaries of a room are replaced by an infinite lattice of image sources [9]. The first-order reflections are geometrically determined by assuming perfectly reflecting walls [8], whereas higher-order reflections are typically modeled by artificial reverberation.

2.3 Delay Networks

Delay networks are fast and efficient, but cannot directly model a given physical space. The most common recursive linear time-invariant reverberator is known as the Feedback Delay Network (FDN). An FDN is built by a number of delay lines in a feedback loop utilizing matrices for attenuation and filtering. Ideally the loop should be lossless, thus energy-preserving [8]. Absorption filters can be designed to obtain a desired reverberation time in various frequency bands [4]. The FDN offers high quality reverberation at an efficient cost, and with the right delay-lines and filter matrices precise models can be made. It however lacks the source and positions updates.

2.3.1 Digital Waveguide Network

A digital waveguide is a bidirectional delay with a port-impedance where traveling waves propagate and scatter if there is a discontinuity in the medium [10]. *Digital Waveguide Networks* (DWNs) are an example of a *delay network*, consisting of a closed network of digital waveguides interconnected by *scattering junctions* [10]. A scattering junction, shown on Fig. 2 is placed where the traveling sound waves hit e.g., the walls of a room (blue boxes on Fig. 1). The sound pressure $p_J(n)$ at such a junction J at the time instant n is calculated as:

$$p_J(n) = \frac{2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \Gamma_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \Gamma_i p_i^+(n), \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of waveguides connected at the scattering junction, Γ_i is the admittance of waveguide i , and p_i^+ is the incoming traveling pressure wave to the junction from waveguide i .

Figure 2. A scattering junction, where the junction pressure is p_J .

These junctions are lossless so that the signal power is conserved [8]. The outgoing pressure wave p_i^+ from the junction is then calculated by

$$p_i^-(n) = p_J(n) - p_i^+(n). \quad (2)$$

The operations in Eqs. 1 and 2 can be combined into a single matrix operation so that the reflected waves are calculated by multiplication of scattering matrix \mathbf{S} with a vector of incoming waves. The network topology and waveguide impedances can be determined from geometrical analysis of a given environment to be simulated based on a path-tracing algorithm [10].

2.3.2 Scattering Delay Network

The scattering delay network extends the digital waveguide network [4] and provides a computationally efficient approximation to geometric ray tracing [11]. The method is conceptually similar to feedback delay networks (FDN) (see above). The SDN involves, however, discrete nodes instead of a circulant matrix. These nodes are connected by a set of waveguides and represent the first-order reflection points of a given space. The nodes are also referred to

as scattering junctions and are interconnected via bidirectional waveguides.

A detailed description of SDC can be found in [4] and [5]. The SDN is an efficient and effective reverberator for acoustic room simulation, providing accurate first-order reflections and rich higher order reflections [4]. For more complex systems involving objects such as rigid cylinders rather than just planes, it requires directional filtering [5]. In addition, the importance of precise first-order and second-order reflections in the modelling of outdoor acoustic spaces is indicated in a previous study [12]. The Waveguide Web offers this type of modelling and will be described in the next section.

2.3.3 The Waveguide Web

The WGW is, in essence, very similar to SDN, but it offers additional accuracy. Like the SDN, the modeled space consists of wall-nodes connected to each other with bidirectional delay lines. The source and receiver are also connected to the wall-nodes by unidirectional delay lines. The main difference between the two algorithms is the scattering action at each node [5]. SDN only allows for one filtering operation at each node. WGW allows for directionally dependent filtering to be implemented, which means that each node can provide different filtering according to where the incoming pressure wave signal is coming from. This can be done to second-order reflection precision. The nodes can be placed at any 3D position, just like SDN.

Full details of WGW computation can be found in [5], and a MATLAB implementation of the algorithm is available online at [13].

2.3.4 Evaluation of the SDN and WGW

A comparison between SDN and WGW for the same space (a shoebox room of 9x7x4 meters) was performed in [5]. The results proved that the two algorithms produced identical first-order reflections and similar reverberation tails, with a noticeable difference due to the different characterization of the higher-order reflections. An evaluation of the computational requirements of WGW was also performed. For the simplest case of 5 nodes, the simulation required 4.36 seconds and 5.65 MB of memory to produce 1 second of audio at a sample rate of 48 kHz. For higher numbers of nodes, the computational requirements increased exponentially, where a case of 30 nodes would require 667.23 seconds and 102 404.16 MB of memory. This exponential increase is due to the N^2 at each node, which means an increase of $N(N^2) = N^3$ filters for the entire system [5]. To our knowledge, no perceptual evaluation of SDN or WGW have been carried out previously.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The SDN and WGW were implemented on Unity. For prototyping, a virtual room was created. It contains the following essential objects, which can be all identified in Fig. 1b : 1) A sound source, to which reverberator and reflection finder scripts, and an Audio Source component are attached (a drone in Fig. 1b). 2) A listener, with a rigid

body and a mesh collider attached to it, so that it can be hit by rays. The Main Camera is snapped to the position and orientation of the listener object. 3) Boundary objects, which set the colliders for the surfaces that are to reflect the emitted rays to the listener. In Fig. 1b the boundaries are simply the walls of a room. 4) Scattering Junctions are the blue boxes shown at the points of first-order reflections. The scattering junctions are instantiated, when the first-order reflection points have been calculated.

The reflection path (the red lines on Fig. 1) holds the audio source position, destination position (the listener position), a ray list for every ray segment, and a float list containing the lengths of these segments. For each first-order reflection, there are two segments: one from source to wall-node, and one from wall-node to receiver. The reflection finder is a component on the source object. The direct path between the source and the listener is easy to find by utilizing the built-in ray tracing system in Unity. The component finds a pre-specified number of reflections, which is generally 6 for first-order reflections in an empty rectangular room. To find the reflections for each surface of the room model the spherical Fibonacci point set algorithm [14] is utilized. The main WGW component receives the list of paths and instantiates the WGW node objects at the positions of the first-order reflections points. These nodes are depicted by the blue boxes on Figure 1.

The WGW nodes hold the scattering position in the environment, a list of connections to the other nodes, two delay lines for input and output, N^2 absorptive IIR filters, the reflection path which the node is placed upon, and finally the scattering values which are applied through a for-loop.

The WGWnode class is based on the node structure proposed by [5]. It holds a class definition for delay lines, a function for propagating through the network, a class definition for the WGW connections (connections between all the other nodes), a function for performing the scattering operation and the initializing of the audio streaming thread. When a number of WGW nodes have been instantiated, they are all connected with bidirectional delay lines. Filters and coefficients for second-order reflections were defined according to [5].

3.1 Performance: Running the WGW in real-time

The WGW was not able to produce output in real-time in our Unity application, even when we set all the filters to constant coefficients. The algorithm was verified by letting the WGW run and record the output offline. For six nodes, the system spent averagely 100 ms for each sample, which is far from real-time. Therefore, to be able to make a real-time simulation for interactive tests, we generated an impulse response and performed convolution-based reverberation, with Unity's Native Audio Plugin SDK [15]. This process of generating an impulse response can took up to 4-5 seconds, which fits the results from [5], where the computational benchmark found the WGW to generate 1 second of audio in 4.35 seconds. This means that upon finding a new reflection path (when either source position or listener position is updated), it will take 4-5 seconds before the audio output from the convolution reverb will ac-

tually be based on the current position. Therefore we have designed an evaluation on the fixed source and listener positions.

4. EVALUATION

Before the perceptual tests, we first compared the impulse responses generated with SDN and WGW and validated our implementation. In a virtual room in Unity (see Fig. 5, scaled to a 9x7x4 meter shoebox room modeled and evaluated in [5], the wall reflectance coefficient was set to 0.97, and the filters in both simulations were designed as allpass filters. Both the impulse response and the T30 plots gave similar results; so we proceeded to the perceptual tests, by asking the participants if they prefer one rendering over the other. In addition to the sounds processed with SDN and WGW, an unprocessed anechoic sound was also used as a control condition.

4.1 The virtual environment and stimuli

The room was designed in Unity, based on geometries identical to the signal comparison. These geometries produce a room that would be considered quite large in a real-world setting. Since it would be difficult to assess the size of the room without any relative elements, some objects were implemented as seen in Figure 3. The room needed to remain empty, for the modeled reverberation would not consider diffusion of furniture and other objects. Therefore only a door and windows were added to the room, since they are flat and would not alter the room reflections. The door is scaled relative to the 4 meter tall wall. Buildings, grass and road objects are added to the background, for a parallax effect when looking through the windows, to obtain a greater sense of depth. To make the room more relatable, textures were added to floor, wall and ceiling as seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A virtual environment that represents a large room (9x7x4 m).

All decisions regarding the size of objects, textures, lighting and materials have been made without precise measurements or references. Neither has the environment been tested for verification of its perceived size. Therefore, there

was a risk that the participants will not be able to perceive the actual size of the room. Nevertheless, it should not affect the end results, since the condition will be the same for all cases.

The input sounds for the perceptual test were recorded in an anechoic room. The sounds were the impact of a ball hitting a surface and a small speech excerpt. These two sounds served as the input for the sound source in two different conditions. One condition shows the character speaking (see Figure 3) while the other condition shows a ball bouncing. The sounds were pre-rendered for the experimental test. The test was designed to take the participant through three different positions in the same room. Therefore a recording for each sound (ball and speech) and reverberation type, was recorded at each of the three positions, producing 12 audio files. A wall reflectance coefficient of 0.97 was empirically chosen for the recordings. Both reverberators had identical filters (allpass). Similar settings were used for the original evaluation of WGW [5]. The two original anechoic recordings were used as the control condition.

All sounds were normalized, and played over a laptop with headphones to the participants. A 13-inch Macbook Pro was used to display the room and record the ratings.

4.2 Experimental Design

The design of this test follows the method proposed by [16] to evaluate the audio quality of synthetic sound effects. In this method, the participant is asked to evaluate a number of sound samples on a scale from *very unrealistic* to *very realistic*. Different adjectives were used in our test on the scale for the specific context in the virtual room, since *realistic* is too general in this case. The interest is to know how realistic the audio output is in the given context of the room and sound source position, therefore the scale is formulated as in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The scale in discrete steps in our test.

The participants were asked to evaluate a total of 18 cases, consisting of combinations between three different room positions, two different sound sources and three different types of processing (SDN, WGW and anechoic). The test started with a quick tour of the room, where the camera moved around in a fluent motion in the room to show the surrounding space, ensuring that the participant was well-aware of the room dimensions and their position in the room. Thereafter the source and listener positions were initialized to one of the three test positions and the test began. The first half of the test instantiated one sound source, and the second half instantiated the other sound source. Half of the participants was first introduced to the speaking character, while the other half was first introduced to the bouncing ball. The order of position and reverberation combinations were completely random. When the participants had completed the test, they were asked to answer a

short questionnaire, where they were allowed to comment on the environment, sound, and perceived room size.

4.3 Results

20 participants completed the tests. Their audio quality ratings were recorded together with the labels for sound, position, and the algorithm used. The minimum rating corresponding to *very poorly* was 0, and the maximum rating corresponding to *very well* was 10.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the experimental conditions. The top part shows the results derived from the overall ratings. These have been labeled by WGW, SDN and Anechoic, and is not dependent on the sound source or position. Anechoic was a control condition and was expected to have a low mean, which it definitely had compared to the two other ratings. The ratings for SDN were generally slightly higher than WGW.

The two other parts in Table 1 show the ratings depending on sound source and position respectively. These ratings are independent of algorithm type, and merely represent the total ratings for the given conditions. This is done to evaluate whether some of the conditions were biased.

Algorithm	Mean	STD
WGW	5.76	1.15
SDN	6.32	1.30
Anechoic	3.31	1.76

Sound	Mean	STD
Ball	5.30	1.16
Speech	4.96	0.97

Position	Mean	STD
Pos 1	5.28	1.06
Pos 2	4.79	1.15
Pos 3	5.32	1.17

Table 1. Statistics of the ratings. Top: General ratings independent of sound source or position. Middle: Overall ratings (independent from algorithm) for the ball and speech respectively. Bottom: Overall ratings (independent from algorithm) for the various positions

Figure 5 visualizes the ratings as a graph with error bars. The ratings between different sources (ball, speech) and different positions (1-3) are similar, and the standard deviations are generally small for all cases. The mean ratings of Algorithm on were tested for normal distribution using the Anderson Darling test. All three ratings were classified as being normally distributed. Therefore, we concluded that the data is parametric, and a parametric statistical test can be used to test for a significant difference. Our null-hypothesis yielded: *There is no difference between the ratings of audio quality in sound processed with respectively SDN and WGW.*

A t-test was performed for three conditions on algorithms; it successfully rejects the null-hypothesis with a probability value of 0.0396 (0.4 percent probability of a type 1 error). Thereby it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the ratings of SDN and WGW, with a preference towards SDN.

Figure 5. Rating statistics visualized as a graph with error bars.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented an implementation and evaluation of the Scattering Delay Network and the Waveguide Web as acoustical renderers in virtual environments on a popular game engine. Following the related background and the presentation of the object-oriented design structure, studies were presented to evaluate the perceptual differences between the two artificial reverberators. A perceptual test was performed, where participants were asked to rate how well they thought the audio output fit into a given environment. The ratings indicate a difference between the reverberators, with a preference of SDN over WGW and anechoic sound. This result is surprising, as it shows that for simple room geometries that contain planar surfaces, a simpler implementation based on SDN should suffice.

Further research and development of WGW would be interesting for more complex environments, where SDN would not be sufficient. The present work posed a compromised solution for running WGW in real-time, by generating an impulse response and performing convolution with the input sound. This limits the system to only update the position of the source and listener at the rate of generating the impulse response. This means, that for WGW to run truly real-time some compromises would have to be made to the complexity, and thereby accuracy of the structure.

The Waveguide Web still offers a wide variety of interesting studies for non-real-time purposes, and by modifying the filter calculation in the directionally dependent filtering structure, new types of scattering could be modeled to provide accurate acoustical models of complex spaces and structures. Recent work presents a novel algorithm for generating virtual acoustic effects from AR, with an extra dimension where it scans both the geometry and the materials of the objects of a room, which are used to determine absorption coefficients and filter responses [17]. This algorithm is not real-time either, works indoors, but further development would consider outdoor areas as well. Therefore, there is a need for an algorithm such as the Waveguide Web, especially if it can be made efficient to run in real-time on mobile processors.

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6. REFERENCES

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